

Bioethanol factory based on brewery spent grains: kinetics of diluted acid hydrolysis and plant simulation

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Abstract

In the regions of Cantabria (Spain) and Santa Fe (Argentina) there are many beer factories at different scales. Among all of the waste from these factories, brewer spent grains (BSG) are the main solid waste of the brewing industry comprising around 85 % of the total by-products [1]. Almost 30 % of the starting malted grain ends up as BSG by the end of the brewing process. In other words, every hectolitre of beer generates 15-20 kg of BSG which corresponds to 34 million tonnes of wet BSG generated annually worldwide [2]. BSG is a lignocellulosic feedstock that is generally used as animal feed. Nevertheless, its compositions in terms of lignin (17.6-23.0 %), crystalline cellulose (16.8-36.0 %), and hemicellulose (19.2-29.6 %) make BSG suitable for breaking polysaccharides into simple monomers that can be transformed in phenolic acids, xylitol, activated carbon, organic acids and biofuels [1].

In the biorefining process for biofuel production, one of the bottlenecks is the biomass pretreatment stage. The key in biomass pretreatment is to alter the crystalline structure of cellulose and/or remove lignin by increasing the polysaccharide's accessibility to enzymes improving the enzymatic hydrolysis [3]. Pretreatment steps could fulfill a triple function: (1) remove lignin, (2) depolymerization of hemicellulosic sugars, and (3) improve cellulose accessibility. In this sense, one of the challenges of this work is to demonstrate that not only hemicellulosic sugars but also cellulosic sugars are being released under mild conditions using a cheap acid as a catalyst.

In this context release of cellulosic and hemicellulosic sugars of BSG by diluted acid hydrolysis was assayed. Sugars released at three different temperatures (90 °C, 100 °C, and 120 °C) were performed by mixing BSG (1 % w/v) with 10 mL of 3 % v/v H₂SO₄. Batch experiments were carried out in duplicate in test tubes at twelve times varying from 5 to 420 minutes. Disaccharides (cellobiose), monosaccharides (glucose, xylose, and arabinose), and acetic acid were quantified in HPLC-RID. In a second step, the kinetic parameters of the diluted acid hydrolysis were simulated in Aspen Plus (AP) in a Continuous Stirred Tank Reactor.

Finally, and taking into account the previous kinetic model, the whole process of a second-generation bioethanol plant was simulated in Aspen Plus (AP). A small plant of 24 kg BSG/day (in dry basis) was simulated considering the BSG generated in a local artisan beer factory allocated in the Cantabria region. The results of the simulation showed yields of 0.17 kg ethanol per kg of dried BSG. The end product of the simulated plant is a high-purity ethanol (at around 99.6 %) which is suitable for its use in the transport sector, improving the environmental issues and the economy of the studied regions in Spain and Argentina.

References

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